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March 9th, 2020

Editorial

Dear friend,

We dedicate our forth and last public newsletter within the SUNRISE action to make an overview of this intense last year.

From now on, you can reach us through the just released SUNERGY communication channels.

We are very thankful for your commitment and help in growing up our community. We hope to reach even further under the SUNERGY umbrella, together with **ENERGY-X**, in the way towards a large-scale European initiative for the production of fossil-free fuels and chemicals from renewable energy and abundant molecules (carbon dioxide, water, nitrogen).

The SUNRISE Team

SUNRISE action wrap-up

New SUNERGY communication tools

New SUNERGY communication tools

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Follow us!

Upcoming Events

SUNRISE Sweden Stakeholder Workshop

The Stakeholder event will present the vision and results of SUNRISE-CSA, as well as the plans for the next steps. The audience will learn about the state-of-the-art and the prospects for the future within SUNERGY...

8th UK Solar Fuels Symposium

The Solar Fuels Network (SFN) team warmly welcomes all SFN members

to the 8th annual SFN symposium at the University of Liverpool. At the meeting on the 2nd April presentations will discuss the latest advances in solar-driven fuels research and there will be chances to interact with the rapidly expanding network of researchers in the UK

Latest highlights

SUNERGY Kick-off meeting & Video

Over 100 stakeholders of SUNRISE and ENERGY-X gathered on February 5-6, 2020 in Brussels for the kick-off meeting of SUNERGY, a large-scale R&I initiative in the area of fossil-free fuels and chemicals...

SUNRISE updates its technological roadmap to a clean-energy EU

The SUNRISE roadmap has been updated including supporter's contributions...Check it out!

Solar energy for a carbon-neutral society: Interview with Katrin Mueller

What will happen if we don't achieve negative-emission by the 2nd half of the 21st century? Can we target climate change through solar energy sources? These are some of the questions that we asked our partner Katrin Mueller...

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